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Biomedical Potential of Titanium-Coated Nanocomposites Explored Through Experimental and Electrochemical Analysis

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Abstract

Objective: This study aims to develop and systematically evaluate titanium substrates coated with chitosan-based nanocomposites incorporating PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles via electrodeposition, with emphasis on corrosion resistance, electrochemical stability, and antifungal performance under simulated physiological conditions. **Method:** Coatings were fabricated using controlled electrodeposition in Hank's balanced salt solution to mimic physiological ionic conditions. Key parameters including applied current density, deposition time, bath pH (7.2 ± 0.1), temperature ($37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$), and nanoparticle concentration were carefully regulated to ensure reproducibility. Structural and chemical characterization was performed using UV-Vis, UV-DRS, XRD and FTIR analyses. Corrosion behaviour was evaluated through weight loss measurements, potentiodynamic polarization, cyclic voltammetry, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using a Randles equivalent circuit model. **Findings:** The coatings were dense, uniform, and strongly adherent. Electrochemical studies showed significant corrosion protection, achieving inhibition efficiencies of 99% (CS/PbO) and 98% (CS/Cd and CS/Ce). Increased charge transfer resistance and reduced double-layer capacitance confirmed enhanced barrier formation. Antifungal testing against *Candida albicans* demonstrated improved activity, particularly for CS/Ce coatings. **Novelty:** This work establishes a reproducible electrochemical framework linking deposition parameters with coating performance for advanced titanium-based biomedical implants.

Keywords: Titanium; Chitosan Bio-nanocomposite; Electrodeposition; UV; XRD; FTIR

1 Introduction

Electrodeposition has emerged as a controllable and scalable technique for fabricating functional nanocomposite coatings due to its operational simplicity, low processing temperature, and precise regulation of thickness, morphology, and composition⁽¹⁾. In biomedical surface engineering, this method enables the incorporation of polymers, metals and metal oxides into tailored architectures on conductive substrates such as titanium^{(2), (3), (4), (5)}. Among biopolymers, chitosan has received considerable attention because of its biodegradability, biocompatibility, film-forming capability, and intrinsic antimicrobial behavior. Its cationic nature promotes strong interfacial adhesion and facilitates uniform nanoparticle dispersion, making it an attractive matrix for composite implant coatings^{(6), (7), (8), (9)}.

Titanium and its alloys remain the materials of choice for orthopedic and dental implants; however, their bioinert surface limits antibacterial performance and early-stage tissue integration. Although chitosan-based coatings have been widely reported, most studies focus primarily on single nanoparticle systems or evaluate either corrosion resistance or antimicrobial activity independently. A systematic understanding of how multi-metal nanocomposite incorporation influences electrochemical stability, surface morphology, and biological performance under physiologically relevant conditions remains insufficiently explored⁽¹⁰⁾. Metal and metal oxide nanoparticles such as PbO, Cd, and Ce offer distinct functional advantages. PbO exhibits notable photocatalytic and antimicrobial characteristics, Cd demonstrates strong antibacterial activity through reactive oxygen species generation and membrane disruption; and cerium nanoparticles possess redox-active behavior, antioxidant capability, and emerging biomedical relevance in tissue engineering and neuroprotective applications⁽¹¹⁾. However, their combined integration within a chitosan matrix on titanium substrates and the corresponding structure, property, biofunction relationship have not been comprehensively investigated. The present study addresses this gap by developing electrodeposited chitosan-based PbO/Cd/Ce nanocomposite coatings on titanium and systematically correlating electrochemical parameters, surface characteristics, corrosion resistance. This integrated approach provides a clearer mechanistic understanding and establishes a rational framework for designing multifunctional implant coatings with enhanced biomedical performance.

2 Methodology

Chitosan (degree of deacetylation >75%), lead oxide (PbO), cadmium (Cd), and cerium (Ce) were procured from Sigma-Aldrich and used. A commercial titanium alloy sheet with a working surface area of 1.0 cm² was employed as the substrate. The titanium sheet was cut into dimensions of 40 mm × 10 mm × 1 mm.

2.1 Synthesis of Lead Oxide, Cadmium and Cerium Nanocomposite

Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) was employed as the electrolyte to replicate physiological ionic conditions during electrodeposition. The buffered medium (pH 7.0–7.4) closely simulates body fluid environments, enabling coating formation under biologically relevant conditions and enhancing the translational significance of the developed implant coatings. HBSS was prepared by dissolving NaCl

(8 g), KCl (400 mg), CaCl₂ (140 mg), MgSO₄·7H₂O (100 mg), MgCl₂·6H₂O (100 mg), Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O (60 mg), KH₂PO₄ (60 mg), D-glucose (1 g), and NaHCO₃ (350 mg) in 800 mL distilled water, followed by dilution to 1 L and continuous stirring until complete dissolution.

Electroplating experiments were carried out using a potentiostat coupled with an impedance analyzer (Autolab Model 73022, Metrohm) in a conventional three-electrode cell maintained at 36 °C. The titanium specimen served as the working electrode with an exposed area of 0.1 cm², while a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and a platinum wire functioned as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. Potentiodynamic polarization measurements were conducted in the potential range of –0.5 to +1.5 V versus SCE at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. Experiments were performed at different coating concentrations are Chitosan(0.4g), Lead oxide(0.2g), Cadmium(0.2g) and Cerium(0.2g) enabling controlled deposition of chitosan-based PbO/Cd/Ce nanocomposite coatings with enhanced surface uniformity, adhesion, and corrosion resistance under simulated physiological conditions.

2.2 Characterization

The surface morphology of a CS PbO, Cd and Ce has been investigated. Absorption spectra were verified for Chitosan Lead oxide (PbO), Cadmium (Cd) and Cerium (Ce) by using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu: UV-2550). The Diffuse Reflectance Spectrum (DRS) of the nano-composite had determined using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (ISR-2200 accessory). JASCO NRS-

3100 laser Raman spectroscopy was used to capture the Raman spectra. XRD analysis of the test specimen were conducted by Scintag-XDS-2000 diffractometer with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation (40 kV, 30 mA).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Characterization of CS, PbO, Cd and Ce

3.1.1. UV-Visible Spectral Analysis

Ultraviolet (UV)-visible spectroscopy is a absorption technique in which the molecules absorb UV-visible radiations resulting in the excitation of the electrons from lower to higher energy levels. UV-visible analysis was employed to investigate the formation of chitosan and its composites with PbO, Cd and Ce nanoparticles⁽¹¹⁾. Pure chitosan dissolved in a weak acidic medium exhibited a characteristic absorption band associated with around 330 nm which is attributed to intrinsic electronic transitions ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) within the polymer backbone rather than surface plasmon resonance, since chitosan itself does not possess plasmonic properties. Upon incorporation of nanoparticle, distinct bathochromic shifts were observed. In addition, the observed peaks for CS/PbO (330 to 380) in Figure 1(i) and CS/Cd nanocomposites showed red-shifted absorption maxima at approximately 380 nm in Figure 1(ii), while the CS/Ce system exhibited a peak 330 to 375 nm shown in Figure 1(iii). These shifts indicate strong coordination between chitosan functional groups ($-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{OH}$) and the incorporated nanoparticles, resulting in enhanced electronic coupling within the composite matrix.

The pronounced spectral shifts observed in the titanium-supported electrochemically deposited coatings confirm successful nanocomposite formation and suggest improved interfacial interaction compared to conventional chitosan-based systems. Overall, the UV-Vis analysis validates the effective integration of PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles into the chitosan matrix and highlights the efficiency of the electrochemical deposition approach.

3.1.2. UV-Visible Diffuse Reflectance Spectra [UV-DRS] Investigation

UV-Visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) was employed to investigate the optical characteristics of solid samples, particularly optically rough coatings and powder-based materials. The incorporation of PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles into the chitosan matrix produced marked variations in the reflectance spectra. Chitosan exhibited an absorption edge around 300–350 nm. In contrast, the CS/PbO nanocomposite demonstrated a pronounced red shift extending to approximately 520 nm. Likewise, the characteristic absorption band of chitosan near 350 nm shifted to about 500 nm upon incorporation of Cd nanoparticles, while the CS/Ce nanocomposite displayed a further shift toward nearly 550 nm. These distinct spectral modifications confirm the successful formation of CS/PbO, CS/Cd, and CS/Ce nanocomposites, as illustrated in

The optical band gap energies were determined using the Kubelka–Munk function derived from the DRS data. The calculated band gap value for pristine chitosan was approximately 3.5 eV. Upon nanoparticle incorporation, the band gap is around 2.38 eV for CS/PbO and 2.48 eV for CS/Cd, whereas the CS/Ce composite exhibited about 2.2 eV. The observed red shifts and reduction in band gap energies can be attributed to the interaction between chitosan and the embedded PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles on the titanium surface, which alters the electronic structure and enhances the optical response of the resulting nanocomposites.

3.1.3. X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis demonstrated that the chitosan/PbO (CS/PbO), chitosan/Cd (CS/Cd), and chitosan/Ce (CS/Ce) nanocomposites possess well-defined crystalline structures. The experimental diffraction peaks showed excellent correspondence with standard Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) data, confirming phase purity and the absence of secondary phases or detectable impurities. The XRD patterns of chitosan incorporated with PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles and deposited on titanium under optimized conditions are presented in Figure 2.(vii–ix).

The CS/PbO nanocomposite displayed three prominent reflections at 2θ values around 45° , 54° , and 57° , which were indexed to the (101), (001), and (110) crystallographic planes, respectively, in accordance with JCPDS Card No. 89-07387. The presence of these characteristic planes verifies the crystalline incorporation of PbO nanoparticles within the chitosan matrix. Similarly, the CS/Cd nanocomposite exhibited distinct diffraction peaks corresponding to the (012), (002), and (011) planes JCPDS Card No. 88-0618, confirming the formation of crystalline Cd phases embedded in the biopolymer framework. In the case of the CS/Ce nanocomposite, sharp reflections observed at 2θ values near 45° , 54° , and 57° were assigned to the (111), (100), and (012) planes, respectively, consistent with standard JCPDS data.

The identification of prominent diffraction planes such as (001), (011), and (100) indicates effective coordination and homogeneous dispersion of PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles within the chitosan matrix. The average crystallite sizes were calculated using the Debye–Scherrer equation ($D = K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta$). Chitosan exhibited crystallite sizes in the range of approximately 12–13.1 nm, whereas nanoparticle incorporation increased the size to about 15.2 nm for CS/PbO, 18.2 nm for CS/Cd, and

Fig 1. (i), (ii), (iii) - UV-Visible sepctrum of (a) CS (b) CS/PbO, Cd, Ce nanocomposites. (iv), (v), (vi) - UV-DRS spectrum of (a) CS (b) CS/PbO, Cd, Ce nanocomposites respectively

16.2 nm for CS/Ce. The increase in crystallite dimension suggests improved crystallinity and enhanced structural ordering resulting from nanoparticle integration. In contrast to earlier studies reporting nanoparticle agglomeration within chitosan matrices, the present nanocomposite coatings exhibit a well-resolved diffraction peaks characteristic of a defined hexagonal crystalline structure⁽¹²⁾. These findings highlight the structural integrity, uniform nanoparticle distribution, and effectiveness of the adopted electrochemical deposition method.

3.1.4. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) analysis:

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to examine the functional groups of chitosan (CS) and its PbO, Cd, and Ce based nanocomposites, as presented in Figure 2(x-xii). The spectral features obtained in this investigation of biopolymer-metal nanocomposite systems, while also revealing distinct interaction characteristics associated with the chitosan matrix and the electrochemical deposition approach. The biopolymer-supported metal oxide systems, the principal polymer backbone vibrations were largely preserved after nanoparticle incorporation, with minor band shifts attributed to hydrogen bonding and metal-polymer coordination. A similar trend was observed in the present study, where the characteristic O-H and N-H stretching vibrations (broad band around $3300\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the amide I (C=O) band near $1630\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ remained clearly visible in all nanocomposite spectra. This confirms that the primary chemical structure of chitosan was retained following nanoparticle integration.

Notably, more significant spectral modifications were detected in the low-frequency region ($650\text{--}720\text{ cm}^{-1}$), corresponding to metal-oxygen (M-O) vibrations. For the CS/PbO nanocomposite, the metal-related band shifted from around 670 cm^{-1} to 640 cm^{-1} , indicating effective coordination between PbO nanoparticles and the functional groups of chitosan. In the CS/Cd system, a shift from approximately 694 cm^{-1} to 710 cm^{-1} was observed, suggesting strong Cd interactions. Similarly, the CS/Ce nanocomposite exhibited a noticeable shift from about 720 cm^{-1} to 666 cm^{-1} , confirming coordination between Ce nanoparticles and the chitosan matrix.

Fig 2. (vii), (viii), (ix) - XRD-sepectrum of (a) CS (b) CS/PbO, Cd, Ce nanocomposites. (x), (xi), (xii) - FT-IR spectrum of (a) CS (b) CS/PbO, Cd, Ce nanocomposites respectively

Table 1. Corrosion rate of CS/PbO, CS/Cd and CS/Ce

Nanocomposite	Weight (mg)	Corrosion Inhibition Efficiency (%)	Corrosion rate
CS/PdO	0.4	99	0.0056
CS/Cd	0.4	99	0.0056
CS/Ce	0.4	99	0.0056

Compared with previously reported biopolymer–metal oxide composites⁽¹⁰⁾, the shifts observed in the present system are more pronounced, particularly in the metal–oxygen vibrational region. This enhanced interaction can be attributed to the presence of both amine (–NH₂) and hydroxyl (–OH) functional groups in chitosan, which facilitate stronger metal–ligand coordination and improved nanoparticle stabilization. Overall, the FTIR results clearly demonstrate robust interfacial bonding between PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles and the chitosan framework, confirming the successful formation of stable nanocomposite coatings on the titanium substrate.

3.1.5. Corrosion Studies

In this study⁽⁴⁾, corrosion inhibition of CS/PbO, CS/Cd and CS/Ce nanocomposite on titanium were discussed using weight loss measurement, cyclic voltametry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and potentiodynamic polarization techniques. In this experimental investigation, a titanium sheet having a dimension of 40 mm × 10 mm × 1 mm were selected and the weight of the selected specimen was measured by using Denver instrument, Germany. Solutions such as acid, base, Hank and neutral solutions were extensively included to accelerate the presence of corrosion on the material surface. Since this research

work is focused on the replacement of bone in a human body with the use of titanium sheet. In this connection, Hanks'solution is used as a blank solution. For the span of 144 hours, the titanium specimen was immersed into the Hanks' 100 ml solution to access the corrosion rate were presented in [Table 1].

3.1.6. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

Nyquist plots of chitosan-coated titanium immersed in Hank's solution, the isolation and existence of PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticle coatings, are presented in Figures 3(xiii–xv). The impedance spectra were analyzed to extract the principal electrochemical parameters, namely charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and double layer capacitance (C_{dl}). The EIS data were fitted using an equivalent electrical circuit model of the form (R_s, Q_{dl}, R_{ct}), where R_s represents the solution resistance, R_{ct} corresponds to the charge transfer resistance at the coating/electrolyte interface, and Q_{dl} is a constant phase element (CPE) accounting for the non-ideal capacitive behavior of the electrical double layer. All Nyquist plots exhibited a single depressed semicircular arc, indicating that the corrosion mechanism is predominantly governed by charge transfer at the metal–electrolyte interface. The diameter of the semicircle is directly related to R_{ct} , with larger diameters signifying enhanced corrosion resistance.

Fig 3. (xiii), (xiv), (xv) - EIS-spectrum of (a) CS (b) CS/PbO, Cd, Ce nanocomposites. (xvi), (xvii), (xviii) - Potentiodynamic polarization of (a) CS (b) CS/PbO, Cd, Ce nanocomposites respectively

For chitosan-coated titanium, the relatively small semicircle diameter indicates lower interfacial resistance and higher electrolyte accessibility. Upon the incorporation of nanoparticle, a pronounced increase in R_{ct} along with a substantial decrease in C_{dl} was observed. In particular, the R_{ct} value increased from 125 to $800 \Omega\text{cm}^2$ for the CS/PbO coating, from 125 to $960 \Omega\text{cm}^2$ for CS/Cd, and from 125 to $812 \Omega\text{cm}^2$ for CS/Ce. Concurrently, the C_{dl} values decreased from 78 to $4.7 \mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ for CS/PbO, to $3.8 \mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ for CS/Cd, and to $4.6 \mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ for CS/Ce coatings. Comparable electrochemical responses have been reported and the impedance behavior in simulated physiological solutions closely matching the trends, observed in the present work⁽¹³⁾. The substantial increase in charge transfer resistance and decrease in double layer capacitance clearly indicates improved corrosion resistance and enhanced barrier properties of the nanocomposite coatings. The reduction in C_{dl} suggests limited electrolyte penetration and the formation of a more compact and stable electrical double layer at the coating/electrolyte interface.

Table 2. Electrochemical Impedences

Electrodes	Charge Transfer Resistance R_{ct} (Ωcm^2)	Double Layer Capacitance C_{dl} ($\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$)	IE_{imp} %
Ti	125	78	90
Ti-CS/PbO	800	4.7	99
Ti-CS/Cd	960	3.8	98
Ti-CS/ Ce	812	4.6	98

The variation of R_{ct} and C_{dl} values for all systems is summarized in Table 2.

3.1.7. Potentiodynamic polarization

Potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out to evaluate the corrosion behaviour of nanoparticle coated titanium in Hank's solution. The polarization curves were recorded by scanning the potential from -0.5 to $+1.5\text{V}$ vs. saturated calomel electrode (SCE) shown at a scan rate of

Table 3. Corrosion Parameters in Hanks'solution

Electrodes	Corrosion potential (mV)	Current density ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	Anodic Tafel slope ($\text{mV}/\text{dec}^{-1}$)	Cathodic Tafel slope ($\text{mV}/\text{dec}^{-1}$)	CIE (%)
Ti	-512	2.29	77	238	90
Ti-CS/PbO	-432	2.04	256	144	99
Ti-CS/Cd	-432	2.10	238	225	98
Ti-CS/Ce	-426	1.16	190	204	98

50 mV s^{-1} . The corresponding inhibition efficiencies and electrochemical parameters tabulated in [Table 3]. For cathodic regions of both the polarization graphs, the corrosion potential (E_{corr}) and current density (i_{corr}) were determined using Tafel extrapolation technique. For titanium coated with CS/PbO, CS/Cd and CS/Ce nanoparticles, E_{corr} shifted towards more positive value, whereas the i_{corr} value is significantly decreased. This could be noticed that with all coats the anodic and cathodic Tafel slope remain quite constant as per the electrochemical parameters (i_{corr} , E_{corr}). This analysis showed the substantially higher intensity of the coated film in Hanks' solution over titanium, which would have the potential to reduce the corrosion surface besides trapping metal surface active sites. PbO Nanocomposites, Cd Nanocomposites and Ce Nanocomposites have smaller i_{corr} and more favourable E_{corr} values, indicating minimal corrosion rates. Similar corrosion inhibition behavior has been reported for chitosan- nanocomposite coatings⁽¹⁴⁾. The corrosion inhibition efficiencies were found to be 99% for CS/PbO and 98% for both CS/Cd and CS/Ce. These results illustrates that the nanocomposite coating predominantly suppress anodic dissolution while also influencing cathodic reactions, it implies that the protective layer established upon this surface of the metal. The polarization behavior of coated samples are shown in [Figures 3(xvi-xviii)].

3.1.8. Biological Application

The antifungal activity of CS/PbO, CS/Cd, and CS/Ce nanocomposites against *Candida albicans* was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method, and the results are summarized in Tables 4– 6. This method was selected due to its suitability for assessing the diffusion-based antifungal efficacy of polymeric and nanoparticle-based coatings, allowing direct measurement of inhibition zone diameters as an indicator of growth suppression. In the present study, pure chitosan-coated titanium served as the negative control to distinguish the intrinsic antifungal effect of chitosan from that of the metal-incorporated systems. Pure chitosan exhibited limited antifungal activity, with inhibition zones increasing slightly from 0 to 3 mm as the concentration increased from 20 to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. In contrast, the nanocomposite formulations displayed noticeably improved antifungal performance at equivalent concentrations. Detectable inhibition (approximately 1 mm) was evident for the nanocomposites even at lower concentrations (20–40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$), whereas pristine chitosan showed minimal or no activity in this range.

At the highest tested concentration (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$), inhibition zones of 5 mm were recorded for both CS/PbO and CS/Cd, while CS/Ce demonstrated the greatest activity with a maximum zone of 6 mm. The negative control (glacial acetic acid, 10 $\mu\text{l}/\text{disc}$) produced no inhibition, confirming that the antifungal effect resulted from the nanocomposite coatings rather than the solvent.

Table 4. Antifungal activity of CS and CS/PbO nanocomposite

Nanocomposites	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Organism/zone of inhibition(mm)	
		<i>Candida albicans</i>	
		CS	CS/PbO
Samples	20	0	1
	40	1	1
	60	1	2
	80	2	4
	100	3	5
Control G (glacial acetic acid)	10 μl /disc	0	0

Table 5. Antifungal activity of CS and CS/Cd nanocomposite

Nanocomposites	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Organism/zone of inhibition(mm)	
		<i>Candida albicans</i>	
CS	CS/Cd		
Samples	20	0	1
	40	1	1
	60	1	2
	80	2	4
	100	3	5
Control G (glacial acetic acid)	10 μl /disc	0	0

Upon the incorporation of metal or metal oxide nanoparticles significantly enhanced the antifungal properties of chitosan. Among the tested formulations, CS/Ce exhibited the strongest activity, followed by CS/PbO and CS/Cd, which showed similar performance. The overall order of antifungal effectiveness was: CS/Ce > CS/PbO \approx CS/Cd .

The enhanced antifungal performance of the nanocomposites can be attributed to synergistic mechanisms, including disruption of fungal cell wall integrity, increased generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and controlled release of metal ions, which collectively interfere with cellular metabolism and suppress fungal proliferation. Representative images of the inhibition zones Figure 4, have been included to visually support the quantitative data presented in Tables 4– 6. These images confirm the uniform diffusion pattern and clearly demonstrate the increased antifungal effectiveness of nanoparticle-incorporated coatings compared to pure chitosan.

Fig 4. Inhibition Zone image of CS, CS/PbO, CS/Cd, CS/Ce

Table 6. Antifungal activity of CS and CS/Ce nanocomposite

Nanocomposites	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Organism/zone of inhibition(mm)	
		<i>Candida albicans</i>	
		CS	CS/Ce
Samples	20	0	1
	40	1	1
	60	1	2
	80	2	4
	100	3	6
Control G (glacial acetic acid)	10 μl /disc	0	0

4 Conclusion

The present investigation successfully reports the development of chitosan-based bio-nanocomposite coatings incorporating PbO, Cd, and Ce nanoparticles on titanium substrates through an electrochemical deposition method. UV-Visible and UV-DRS studies verified nanoparticle incorporation, evidenced by characteristic absorption features and reduced band gap energies. XRD analysis confirmed the crystalline nature of the coatings with prominent peaks corresponding to a hexagonal structure, while FT-IR results indicated effective interaction between chitosan functional groups and the incorporated nanoparticles. Electrochemical corrosion studies carried out in Hank's solution demonstrated excellent protective behavior. The corrosion inhibition efficiency reached 99% for CS/PbO and 98% for both CS/Cd and CS/Ce coatings, indicating the formation of a dense and adherent protective barrier. The observed increase in charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and decrease in double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) further confirmed the formation of a compact and stable coating on the titanium surface. Antifungal evaluation revealed that nanoparticle-modified chitosan exhibited markedly enhanced activity against *Candida albicans* compared to pristine chitosan. Among the formulations, CS/Ce showed the highest inhibition, followed by CS/PbO and CS/Cd. The results clearly demonstrate that the integration of metal or metal oxide nanoparticles substantially improves both the anticorrosive behavior and antifungal efficacy of chitosan-based coatings. The combined functional properties of these nanocomposites emphasize their considerable potential for use in biomedical devices and implant-related applications.

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References

- 1) Wang Y, Liu R, Ma Y, Shen X, Wang D. Electrodeposition of Metal Nanoparticles inside Carbon Nanopipettes for Sensing Applications. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.2c04449>.
- 2) Strnad S, Zemljic LF. Cellulose-chitosan functional biocomposites. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15020425>.
- 3) Priscilla S, Venkatasubbu GD, Mohideen SS. Chitosan-Coated Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles for Antimicrobial Applications. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793292024501224>.
- 4) Pragathiswaran C, Thulasi G, Al-Ansari M, Al-Humaid LA, Saravanan M. Experimental investigation and electrochemical characterization of titanium coated nanocomposite materials for biomedical applications. *Journal of Molecular Structure*. 2021;1231:129932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2021.129932>.
- 5) Samejo S, Baig JA, Kazi T. Chitosan-integrated TiO₂ nanocomposite for adsorptive removal of Cd and Pb from drinking water. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11696-024-03637-6>.
- 6) Li J, Gong Y, Xue Y, Zhang H, Xu L, Wang S. Magnetron sputtering to enhance bone integration of tantalum-coated titanium implants: an in vitro and in vivo analysis. *BMC Biotechnology*. 2025;25:94. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12896-025-01032-x>.
- 7) Fuster MG, Montalban MG, Carissimi G, Lima B. Antibacterial Effect of Chitosan-Gold Nanoparticles and Computational Modeling of the Interaction between Chitosan and a Lipid Bilayer Model. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10122340>.
- 8) Rani UC, Pragathiswaran C, Balakrishnan D, Selvarani K, Smitha C. TiO₂@ZnO-CdS Nanocomposites for Sensing and Cytotoxicity Applications. *International Journal of Zoological Investigations*. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.33745/ijzi.2022.v08i0s.001>.
- 9) Harish R, Nisha KD, Prabakaran S, Sridevi B, Harish S, Navaneethan M, et al. Cytotoxicity assessment of chitosan coated CdS nanoparticles for bio-imaging applications. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2019.143817>.
- 10) Elfadl AA, Bashal AH, Habeeb TH, Khalafalla MAH, Alkayal NS. Preparation, Characterization, Dielectric Properties, and AC Conductivity of Chitosan Stabilized Metallic Oxides CoO and SrO; Experiments and Tight Binding Calculations. *Polymers*. 2023;15(20):4132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15204132>.
- 11) Pragathiswaran C, Anusuya N, Mary VJ. A potential catalyst - TiO₂/ZnO based chitosan gel beads for the reduction of nitro-aromatic compounds aggregated sodium borohydride and their antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Molecular Structure*. 2021;1236(3):130197.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2021.130197>.

- 12) Syed A, Yadav LSR, Bahkali AH, Elgorban AM, Hakeem DA, Ganagnappa N. Effect of CeO₂-ZnO Nanocomposite for photocatalytic and Antibacterial Activities. *Crystals*. 2020;10(9):817. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst10090817>.
- 13) Bairagi H, Vashishth P, Narang R, Shukla SK, Mangla B. Protection of mild steel from corrosion in an aggressive chloride media through chitosan-CeO₂ nanocomposite: Experimental and computational studies. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corcom.2023.08.003>.
- 14) Nedumaran N, Suresh N, Gurumoorthy K. Fabrication of polydopamine with silver nanoparticles coating on titanium to enhance corrosion resistance: An in vitro analysis. *Journal of Pioneering Medical Sciences*. 2025;14(06):138-145. <https://doi.org/10.47310/jpms2025140619>.